

**MODELING USING LINEAR AND POLYNOMIAL
REGRESSION ALGORITHMS OF MACHINE LEARNING
BASED ON MAHALLA DATA**

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the problem of creating a model and algorithm to support the importance of monitoring in the management of socio-economic processes in self-government bodies, decision-making in self-government bodies through machine learning. Models and algorithms of the decision-making process in digital form are studied, consisting of independent data, quantitative parametric assessments of the activities of self-government bodies and general expert assessments of self-government bodies. This model is used to quantify the generalized expert assessment of the condition of the object of the new self-government body, which is interpreted as a proposed improvement solution.

Introduction: When analyzing the data of mahallas, information that determines the well-being, material and spiritual state of the population is often found. The standard of living of the population is the level of provision of people with necessary material and spiritual goods, the level of satisfaction of their consumption and needs.[1,2]

The standard of living is:

- in a narrow sense, it is understood as meeting the needs of the population, providing them with income and expenses;
- In a broad sense, it refers to the level of human development (health status, needs) and living conditions (environment, safety).

In general, the standard of living of the population is classified as follows::

- completeness (the ability to fully enjoy the benefits that ensure the harmonious development of a person);
- normative level (a scientifically based rational level of consumption that ensures the reproduction of a person's physical and intellectual abilities);
- Poverty (the possibility of using material goods in the reproduction of labor at the lower limit);

The standard of living of the population can be considered as the level of satisfaction of material, spiritual and social needs. One of the most important indicators in this regard is the employment of the local population. Incomplete employment data is common when data is collected by community, but information data is lost if it is not taken into account during the initial data processing. As a result, errors in checking the adequacy of the model increase when constructing the model. To solve the problem, you can build a model using machine learning methods and algorithms based on the available data and predict the drop rate based on the built model.

Regression is one of the methods of data mining, a set of statistical processes for evaluating the relationships between variables related to an object or process. Regression analysis is linear. Regression analysis is mainly used for forecasting and predicting, and currently the use of this method is consistent with the field of machine learning [3]. In linear regression, a line indicating the relationship between the two variables usually represents the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. The corresponding line is called the regression line, and

$y=a*x+b$ is represented by the linear equation type. If we have several independent variables, if we take the following model, then we are talking about multilinear regression: [4]

$$y=b_0+b_1*x_1+b_2*x_2+\dots+b_n*x_n$$

* y — response to values, i.e. represents the result estimated by the model.

* intersection of b_0 , where x is equal to y and they are all 0.

* the first symbol of b_1 x_1 coefficient 1;

* coefficient of another attribute x_n ;

* $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ are independent model variables.

Basically, the equation explains the relationship between a continuously bound variable (y) and two or more independent variables

($x_1, x_2, \dots$) In polynomial regression, the relationship between independent variables and bound variables is usually realized through a polynomial, which denotes the relationship between two variables.

To assess the employment of the population of a microdistrict, more than a hundred microdistricts are considered according to the following parameters.[5]

Table 1. Employment indicators sector by sector

Mahalla	Number of people employed in enterprises and organizations	Number of people employed in entrepreneurship	Number of people engaged in folk crafts	Number of people employed in trade	Number of people employed in animal husbandry, poultry farming and beekeeping	Employment in other areas of entrepreneurship	Number of people who went abroad for a long time in search of work	Number of people with permanent jobs
Ustalar	114	19	0	9	3	4	312	486
Yuksalish	137	12	0	7	3	5	421	617
Nmuna	75	8	1	4	14	27	83	64
Gulzor	423	14	0	12	457	11	489	423
Bogzor	100	22	5	4	6	7	147	0
Uzbeksthan	126	32	3	29	8	3	316	811
Navbahor	281	21	0	19	5	2	285	281

he population's employment is plotted based on the following parameters, as shown in Table 1 by the column section, and those employed in the neighborhood are divided into groups. This is the number of people employed in enterprises and organizations, the number of people employed in entrepreneurship, the number of people employed in home-based work, the number of people employed in folk crafts, the number of people employed in trade, the number of people engaged in animal husbandry, poultry farming and beekeeping, the number of people employed in other

areas of entrepreneurship, the number of people who have been looking for work in foreign countries for a long time, the number of constantly employed people.[6,7]

Based on this information, a model for assessing the employment of the population of more than five hundred mahallas of the Khorezm region will be built using the KNIME Analytics Platform. To do this, we use the KNIME Analytics Platform to perform the following tasks:

KNIME Analytics Platform.

Based on the workflow shown in Figure 2, the algorithm calculation processes are performed as follows.[8]

1. CSV Reader: This component loads data. The uploaded data will look like this:

Row ID	Column0	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8
Row0	114	19	0	0	9	3	4	312	486
Row1	137	12	0	0	7	3	5	421	617
Row2	75	8	0	1	4	14	27	83	64
Row3	423	14	0	0	12	457	11	489	423
Row4	100	22	0	5	4	6	7	147	0
Row5	126	32	1	3	29	8	3	316	811
Row6	281	21	0	0	19	5	2	285	281
Row7	236	53	0	0	46	19	11	342	786
Row8	311	52	1	5	4	31	10	280	481
Row9	181	46	0	0	44	16	11	345	781
Row10	102	7	0	0	10	2	3	275	102
Row11	468	94	4	17	23	7	8	315	468
Row12	268	59	0	0	11	9	11	384	842
Row13	701	56	14	13	10	16	8	327	921
Row14	237	56	5	8	15	26	3	227	915
Row15	1554	354	2	1	16	314	21	335	1554
Row16	187	15	0	0	5	0	10	418	187
Row17	145	16	0	0	15	1	0	146	781
Row18	678	48	0	0	12	32	12	171	781
Row19	781	46	0	0	18	16	12	85	781
Row20	126	66	32	26	44	88	23	306	126
Row21	556	186	54	4	28	57	43	509	556
Row22	262	17	0	0	7	14	8	227	262
Row23	131	11	0	0	8	1	0	297	781
Row24	778	48	0	0	5	32	12	252	781

Figure 3. The database necessary for constructing the algorithm of employment indicators industry by industry is formed.

1. Normalizer: This component normalizes the data we have (minmax normalizes the interval [0..1]). This process is necessary to give the same weight to all characters).

Row ID	Column0	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8
Row0	0.019	0.022	0	0	0.013	0.002	0.023	0.436	0.183
Row1	0.029	0.013	0	0	0.01	0.002	0.029	0.589	0.232
Row2	0.003	0.008	0	0.031	0.006	0.011	0.158	0.116	0.024
Row3	0.146	0.016	0	0	0.017	0.353	0.064	0.684	0.159
Row4	0.014	0.026	0	0.156	0.006	0.005	0.041	0.206	0
Row5	0.024	0.039	0.018	0.094	0.04	0.006	0.018	0.442	0.305
Row6	0.088	0.025	0	0	0.026	0.004	0.012	0.399	0.106
Row7	0.069	0.066	0	0	0.064	0.015	0.064	0.478	0.295
Row8	0.1	0.065	0.018	0.156	0.006	0.024	0.058	0.392	0.181
Row9	0.047	0.057	0	0	0.061	0.012	0.064	0.483	0.293
Row10	0.014	0.006	0	0	0.014	0.002	0.018	0.385	0.038
Row11	0.164	0.119	0.07	0.531	0.032	0.005	0.047	0.441	0.176
Row12	0.082	0.074	0	0	0.015	0.007	0.064	0.537	0.316
Row13	0.26	0.07	0.246	0.406	0.014	0.012	0.047	0.457	0.346
Row14	0.07	0.07	0.088	0.25	0.021	0.02	0.018	0.317	0.344
Row15	0.61	0.457	0.035	0.031	0.022	0.242	0.123	0.469	0.584
Row16	0.049	0.017	0	0	0.007	0	0.058	0.585	0.07
Row17	0.032	0.018	0	0	0.021	0.001	0	0.204	0.293
Row18	0.251	0.06	0	0	0.017	0.025	0.07	0.239	0.293
Row19	0.293	0.057	0	0	0.025	0.012	0.07	0.119	0.293
Row20	0.024	0.083	0.561	0.812	0.061	0.068	0.135	0.428	0.047
Row21	0.2	0.239	0.947	0.125	0.039	0.044	0.251	0.712	0.209
Row22	0.08	0.019	0	0	0.01	0.011	0.047	0.317	0.098
Row23	0.026	0.012	0	0	0.011	0.001	0	0.415	0.293
Row24	0.292	0.06	0	0	0.007	0.025	0.07	0.352	0.293

Figure 4. Viewing the data set after normalization.

1. Partitioning: This component divides the data set into two parts. The result is a set of tutorials and tests. In this case, the object is divided into two groups: objects in the set and objects in the test set.(9)

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Err	t- value	P> t
Column 0	-0.2824	0.4278	-0.6602	0.5114
Column 1	2.1185	0.8091	2.6185	0.011
Column 2	1.5139	0.6282	2.4098	0.0182
Column 3	-1.2245	0.5563	-2.2014	0.0305
Column 4	0.3353	0.6907	0.4854	0.6287
Column 5	-0.4798	0.5202	-0.9223	0.3591
Column 6	-2.8187	0.6402	-4.4031	3.19E-5
Column 7	-3.4205	0.3539	-9.6647	3.33E-15
Column 0 ²	3.4503	1.3707	2.5173	0.0143
Column 1 ²	-7.9348	2.7348	-2.8972	0.0051
Column 2 ³	-1.3405	2.4727	-0.5421	0.5896

Figure 5. Coefficients of first-and second-order polynomial variables

The following nonlinear equation is obtained from the obtained data.

$$Y_1 = -0,2824 * x_1 + 2,1185 * x_2 + 0,5753 * x_3 + 0,4496 * x_4 + 0,5498 * x_5 + 0,9686 * x_6 \\ - 1,0917 * x_7 - 0,3426 * x_8 + 3,4503 * x_1^2 - 7,9348 * x_2^2 - 1,3405 * x_3^2 - 1,7137 \\ * x_4^2 + 0,5021 * x_5^2 - 3,3965 * x_6^2 + 3,9315 * x_7^2 + 1,2057 * x_8^2;$$

R-Squared:0.5719

Adjusted R-Squared: 0.4138 getting the result. We can also plot a model constructed using the coefficients found with this component.

Figure 6. Graph of a machine learning model

Regression predictor: We use this component to check the adequacy of the model built with the help of a regression learner. This is done by passing the test sample to the regression predictor. After testing, the Line Chart component is used to visualize how the results differ from the actual situation.

Figure 7. Compare the results using the Line Chart component.

Figure 7 shows the result of the graphical model, represented by red lines, and the results of the graphical test, shown by blue lines. Using this graph, you can understand how the model is adequate to the real situation. In addition, this problem can be solved in the same sequence using the same linear regression algorithm. The coefficients of the polynomial level 1 and the polynomial function constructed in it are as follows. Statistics on Linear Regression

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Err	t- value	P> t
Column0	-1.1489	0.4975	-2.3093	0.0234
Column1	0.8826	0.683	1.2921	0.1999
Column2	1.5139	0.6282	2.4098	0.0182
Column3	-1.2245	0.5563	-2.2014	0.0305
Column4	0.3353	0.6907	0.4854	0.6287
Column5	-0.4798	0.5202	-0.9223	0.3591
Column6	-2.8187	0.6402	-4.4031	3.19E-5
Column7	-3.4205	0.3539	-9.6647	3.33E-15

Offset Value : 2 ; R-Squared: 0.8181; Adjusted R- Squared: 0.8003.

Figure 8. Level 1 and polynomial coefficients obtained by linear regression.

The general form of the degree 1 polynomial obtained by this linear regression method is as follows.

$$Y_1 = -1,1489 * x_1 + 0,8826 * x_2 + 1,5139 * x_3 - 1,2245 * x_4 + 0,3353 * x_5 - 0,4798 * x_6 - 2,8187 * x_7 - 3,4205 * x_8;$$

To check the adequacy of the model obtained using this method, the same testing method as polynomial regression is used, and the following result is obtained.[10]

Figure 9. Comparing the results using the Line Chart component.

From Figure 9, we can see that a comparative analysis that the results obtained using the model differ significantly from the real situation and are no better than the model constructed using polynomial regression. Thus, a model with linear and polynomial regression algorithms of machine learning based on data on districts was considered, using a regression model to supplement data on the employment of all mahallas in the Khorezm region, and two models constructed using this method were compared. For this data set, the model constructed using polynomial regression proved to be more efficient than the model constructed using linear regression.

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